

The Impact of Work Life Policies, Empowerment, Training and Development and Job Satisfaction on Employees Performance with Mediation Organizational Citizenship Behavior

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Abstract. Human resources is a company's very valuable asset that should always be kept level of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) to improve their performance. The purpose of this study to determine the impact of work life polices, empowerment, training and development, job satisfaction on employee performance with OCB as mediation variable in using 140 permanent lectures majoring in management and economics in Batam as respondents. The data analysis technique used is multiple regression analysis, path analysis and Sobel test to test the effect of intervening variable. This study found that OCB can indirectly affect the relationship between work life polices, empowerment, training and development, job satisfaction on employee performance. This result illustrate that the performance of employees will increase as improved OCB, so it is important for the company to pay more attention to the work life polices, empowerment, training and development, job satisfaction so that the employee's satisfaction is always maintained.

Keywords: work polices, empowerment, training and development, job satisfaction, employee performance, OCB

Introduction

Generally every human being is faced with problems in the family environment and the work environment. Gutek (1991) describes the work-life conflict occurs in two ways when family life disrupted due to work and when the work is interrupted for family life. Both of these are critical situations that create a conflict at work. Employees in the university as lecturers have life environment will be served and faced every day, such as the work environment and the family environment. Both of these environments can't be kept out of the conflict of life. Their quality of life

good work of university professors foster a desire to stay and last a long time in the university.

Work-life conflict that faced the lecturer does not reduce the duties and responsibilities of a university lecturer. Lecturers have responsibility for work that can't be attributed to other conflicts. Empowerment is believed to be one of the factors that can help lecturers to fulfill the duties and responsibilities on their job. Sadarusman (2004) describe empowerment is the process of encouraging individuals in the organization to seize the initiative, authority and responsibility in completing the work. Recognizing the importance of empowerment in the university with the aim that the

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lecturer is able to carry out the work and be involved in decision making and problem solving.

Organizations that empowerment employees also need programs such as training and development programs to influence employee performance. Training and development is one way to develop human resources towards the globalization era full of challenges. Training and development can help lecturers finished their work at the moment and can be used throughout his career to help improve future career. Training and development provide the skills, knowledge and ability to do the job well.

Employees who feel satisfaction in their work tend to have a presence and better adherence to regulations, these employees also usually have a better performance compared with employees who do not have the satisfaction in his work. Robbins (2006) states the effect of job satisfaction on employee performance is employee satisfaction at work have a greater possibility to talk about positive things about the organization, helping other employees, and do their work beyond the normal forecast.

To mediate this variable we are used Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) for OCB is one of many factors that affect employee performance. Improve the performance of human resources is very difficult because the employee is required to consistently provide good performance. Organ and Ryan (1995) provides one example of OCB that employees are always ready and willing to go the extra mile to help the work of other employees within the organization. OCB is cooperation undertaken without monetary benefits (Noon and Blyton, 1997). Behavior such as this lecturer is desired by every university because this behavior is outside the employment contract of a university to the faculty and this behavior is very helpful for the university to achieve the goals and objectives of the university.

The purpose of this study was to determine the impact of work-life policies, empowerment, training and development and employee job satisfaction on the performance of the mediation OCB. In this study, we limit the scope of this study, a questionnaire distributed only to tenured faculty of business management in Batam.

Literature Review

Work life Policies

There is an inverse relationship between the role of the problems in working life and employee performance. If the density of the problems in working life is high then the employee's performance will decrease and if the density of the problems in working life is low, the performance of employees will be high (Frone et al, 1992).

According to the theory Quality of work life is said that managers provide an opportunity for workers to design their work on what is needed to make the product or service so that they can work effectively. To improve the knowledge and skills of employees need to be training extensively to increase confidence and comfort in doing the job.

Empowerment

According Cacciope (1998) stated that empowerment is a process where management gives flexibility to the employees to make decisions and take action that will lead to the success of the organization. Employee empowerment is implemented by exploring the potential contained on the employee.

Training and Development

Marihot explain training and development are two concepts are the same, namely to improve the knowledge, skills, and abilities. Training is focused on improving the ability to do specific job at this time, and the development of more focused on improving the knowledge to do the job in the future, which is done through an integrated approach with other activities to change the behavior of labor.

Job Satisfaction

Discrepancy theory, this theory to measure job satisfaction a person by calculating the difference between something that should have been with the perceived reality. Therefore, when satisfaction obtained exceeds that desired, then people will be more satisfied longer, so there is a discrepancy, but it is a positive discrepancy.

Equity theory, this theory suggests that people will feel satisfied or dissatisfied, depending on the presence or absence of fairness (equity) in a situation, particularly the employment situation. According to

this theory the main component in the theory of justice is input, results, justice and injustice. Input is a valuable factor for employees who are considered to support its work, such as education, experience, skills, the number of tasks and equipment or supplies used to do the job.

Two factor theory, according to this theory of job satisfaction and job dissatisfaction that is a different matter. Satisfaction and dissatisfaction with the job rather than a continuous variable. This theory formulated characteristic job into two groups satisfies or motivator and dissatisfied. Satisfies are factors or circumstances required as a source of job satisfaction as interesting work, full of challenges, there are opportunities for achievement, the opportunity to earn rewards and promotions.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior

There are two approaches to the concept of OCB is an extra performance of the separate role of in-role performance or the performance of the corresponding job descriptions. The second approach is to view the OCB of principle or political philosophy. This approach identifies the behavior of members of an organization citizenship behavior. The existence of OCB is the impact of beliefs and perceptions of individuals in the organization of the fulfillment of the covenant relationship and psychological contract. This behavior arises because individual feelings as a member of the organization who have a sense of satisfaction when able to do anything more than the organization (Wulani, 2005).

Employee Performance

Bernardin and Russel (1993) describes the six criteria used to measure the extent to which the performance of individual employees, namely by looking at the quality of work, quantity of work, timeliness, effectiveness, independence and commitment to work and Tjokroaminoto (2007) describes the performance of employees refers to the ability of employees to carry out the overall duties of responsibility. These tasks are usually based on indicators of success that have been defined. As a result it will be known that an employee entered in the levels of specific performance. Handoko (2003) describes the performance of a behavior or actions relevant to the purpose of the organization, where the specification of this vote represents a decision to assessments by experts. The assessment activities can

improve the performance of personnel decisions and provide feedback to employees on the resulting performance.

Nawawi (2001) showed that work-life policies are accepted by employees affected by OCB and will affect the performance generated by the employee. The results of this study found that OCB may mediate the relationship between work-life policies and employee performance.

Empowerment encourage individuals to seize the initiative in this matter in mediation by the OCB in the completion of their work in a timely manner. These results indicate that the empowerment received by employees affected by OCB and will affect the performance generated by the employee (Nurdiansyah, 2001).

OCB may mediate the relationship between the training and development of employees' performance. Training and development provided by the organization can influence the OCB employees and influential for the resulting performance of the employee. The results of this research study Mangkuprawira (2004) who found that OCB may mediate the relationship between the training and development of employees' performance.

OCB may mediate the relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance. Job satisfaction can influence OCB employee and the resulting performance effect for those employees. Research Mangkunagara (2004) who found that OCB may mediate the relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance.

Hypothesis

Each organization expect the best performance from their employees, but the best performance is very difficult to obtain because every employee of the conflict is unavoidable in life, therefore, a good performance was also affected by the policy working life provided by the organization. The views expressed by Sudarsono (2007) that job satisfaction is positively correlated to the quality of working life.

H1: work-life policies have positive influence on employee performance.

Most studies show that employee empowerment also improve employee performance. Empowerment is used in research to affect the performance of the employee one of them so that employees can increasingly have the ability, speed and accuracy in completing the work.

H2: Empowerment positive effect on employee performance.

Training and development of employees obtained can be used throughout his career and may help to improve future career. Training and development also provides the skills, knowledge and ability to do its job properly. For the training and development that will affect the best performance by the employee to the organization.

H3: Training and development positively affects employee performance.

Job satisfaction is basically something individual. Every individual has a level of job satisfaction vary according to his wishes. Job satisfaction one of which can be assessed from the salary or remuneration and other working facilities such as homes or work vehicle of an employee, therefore, job satisfaction affects the performance of employees.

H4: Job satisfaction has positive influence on employee performance.

Emerson (1976) describes something that is offered by an organization will result in liability are different depending on the extent to which individuals are targeted by the bid's value. This value can be perceived benefits depending on personal needs, the needs of professional and family situation of employees, the greater the perceived benefits of more and more employees will give extra behavior to the organization.

H5: work-life policies have positive influence on employee performance with mediation OCB.

Agarwal and Ferratt (1999) found that organizations are now empowering employees to assist organizations in the work and decision-making, using practices such employees feel that the organization provide value to them and then employees will demonstrate commitment to the organization through the OCB.

H6: Empowerment has positive effect on employee performance with mediation OCB.

Kraiger & Ford (2007) describes the training and development is an approach to improve the performance of individuals and organizations and is also considered as human resources practices that are most important to build a relationship that is long for employees. Previous research has evidence about the relationship of training and development and OCB.

H7: Training and development has positive influence on employee performance with mediation OCB.

Job satisfaction is a feeling of satisfaction or dissatisfaction, supported or not supported on the working environment as well as to work. Individuals who feel satisfaction in terms of his work or his environment, will get a better feel and will affect the good behavior and positive impact on the environment and also people who are nearby.

H8: Job satisfaction has positive influence on employee performance with mediation OCB.

One example, according OCB (Organ and Ryan 1995) is where employees are always ready and willing to go the extra mile to help with the work of other employees within the organization without expecting anything in return. If all employees have properties like this then the employee's performance is very good and will benefit the organization as well. In this study, OCB is used as a mediating variable.

H9: OCB positive effect on employee performance

Research Design

This study used a questionnaire given to permanent lecturer Department of Business Management and Economics, University which is located in Batam. The primary data collection through direct help using a questionnaire distributed to respondents who have the research sample. The questionnaire used is Pare (2001) questionnaire for variable life policies work, Rondeau and Lamelin (1997) questionnaire for the empowerment variables, Rogg et al. (2001) questionnaire for a variable training and development, Podsakoff (1990) questionnaire for OCB variable, Teseema and Soeters (2006) questionnaire for variable employee performance and Maharani et al (2014) for variable job satisfaction. Primary data that have been collected and processed by using validity and reliability.

Results and Discussion

The population in this study are all lectures in the University located in Batam Department of Business Management with a number of 214 permanent lecturers. The population was calculated using the

Slovin formula and obtained the sample are used 139 permanent lecturers.

Table 1 Validity Test

Variable	Validity			
	Item	r	r table	result
Work life Policies	Item 1	0.772	0,166	Valid
	Item 2	0.678	0,166	Valid
	Item 3	0.708	0,166	Valid
	Item 4	0.637	0,166	Valid
Empowerment	Item 1	0.443	0,166	Valid
	Item 2	0.512	0,166	Valid
	Item 3	0.609	0,166	Valid
	Item 4	0.606	0,166	Valid
	Item 5	0.521	0,166	Valid
	Item 6	0.498	0,166	Valid
	Item 7	0.607	0,166	Valid
	Item 8	0.571	0,166	Valid
	Item 9	0.737	0,166	Valid
Training and Development	Item 1	0.836	0,166	Valid
	Item 2	0.849	0,166	Valid
	Item 3	0.836	0,166	Valid
	Item 4	0.805	0,166	Valid
	Item 5	0.819	0,166	Valid
	Item 6	0.592	0,166	Valid
Job Satisfaction	Item 1	0.676	0,166	Valid
	Item 2	0.708	0,166	Valid
	Item 3	0.648	0,166	Valid
	Item 4	0.547	0,166	Valid
	Item 5	0.546	0,166	Valid
	Item 6	0.708	0,166	Valid
	Item 7	0.754	0,166	Valid
	Item 8	0.610	0,166	Valid
	Item 9	0.739	0,166	Valid
	Item 10	0.714	0,166	Valid
OCB	Item 1	0.764	0,166	Valid
	Item 2	0.778	0,166	Valid
	Item 3	0.764	0,166	Valid
	Item 4	0.597	0,166	Valid
	Item 5	0.639	0,166	Valid
	Item 6	0.724	0,166	Valid
Employee Performance	Item 1	0.678	0,166	Valid
	Item 2	0.885	0,166	Valid
	Item 3	0.830	0,166	Valid
	Item 4	0.760	0,166	Valid

According to the Table 1, note that each indicator question used have a value of r count larger than r table, which means that the indicator questions of each variable used in this study is valid to be used as a measurement variable.

Table 2 Reliability Test

Variabel	Reliability		
	Alpha		Remarks
	Cronbach	Cut Off Alpha Cronbach	
Work life Policies	0.652	0.60	Reliable
Empowerment	0.728	0.60	Reliable
Train. and Dev.	0.880	0.60	Reliable
Job Satisfaction	0.850	0.60	Reliable
OCB	0.801	0.60	Reliable
Empl. Perform.	0.797	0.60	Reliable

According to the Table 2, each variable has a value of tolerance > 0.10 and VIF <10, so that it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity between independent variables in this regression model.

Table 3 Normality Test

	Unstandardized Residual
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	0,906
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0,384

According to the Table 3, the value of Kolmogorov-Smirnov was 0,906 and 0,384 significance value. The significance value greater than 0.05, so it can be concluded that the data were normally distributed residuals.

Table 4 Multicollinearity Test

Variabel	Tolerance	VIF
Work life Policies	0,925	1,081
Empowerment	0,497	2,010
Training and Development	0,532	1,879
Job Satisfaction	0,517	1,933
OCB	0,683	1,464

According to the Table 4, each variable has a value of tolerance > 0.10 and VIF <10, so that it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity between independent variables in this regression model.

Table 5 Hypotheses Test

Variabel	Sig
Work life Policies	0,111
Empowerment	0,603
Training and Development	0,997
Job Satisfaction	0,194
OCB	0,597

Based on the Table 5, all the independent variables did not significantly affect the dependent variable residual absolute value. This is evident from the significant value that is greater than 0.05.

Regression Analysis Model 1

Table 6 Analysis Model 1 Test

Variabel	Coefficient		T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error		
Constanta	7,135	2,132	3,346	0,001
Work life Policies	0,176	0,076	2,299	0,023
Empowerment	0,198	0,063	3,146	0,002
Training and Development	0,174	0,073	2,399	0,018
Job Satisfaction	0,275	0,054	5,090	0,000

T test results obtained for work life policies amounted to 2,299 t. T table value of 1.656 to 0.05. T

value is greater than 1.656, so it can be concluded there is positive.

The results of the t test for empowerment obtained t count equal to 3,146 with the value t table of 1.656 to 0.05. T value is greater than 1.656, so it can be concluded there is positive between the empowerment of OCB.

T test results obtained to training and development amounted to 2,399 t with t table value of 1.656 to 0.05. T value is greater than 1.656, so it can be concluded there is positive between the training and development of the OCB.

The results of the t test for job satisfaction obtained t calculate equal to 5,090 with t table value of 1.656 to 0.05. T value is greater than 1.656, so it can be concluded there is positive between job satisfaction and OCB.

Regression Analysis Model 2

Table 7 Analysis Model 2 Test

Variabel	Coefficient		B	Std. Error
	B	Std. Error		
Constanta	1,465	1,803	0,812	0,418
Work life Policies	0,081	0,063	2,274	0,030
Empowerment	0,056	0,053	2,054	0,019
Training and Development	0,170	0,060	2,813	0,006
Job Satisfaction	0,139	0,048	2,899	0,004
OCB	0,320	0,070	1,999	0,048

The results of the t test for work-life policies obtained t calculate equal to 2.274 with t table value of 1.656 to 0.05. T value is greater than 1.656, so it can be concluded that H1 is supported which means there is a positive influence between work life policies on employee performance.

The results of the t test for empowerment obtained t count equal to 2.054 with t table value of 1.656 to 0.05. T value is greater than 1.656, so it can be concluded that the H2 is supported, which means there is positive between empowerment on employee performance.

T test results obtained to training and development amounted to 2.813 t arithmetic with t table value of 1.656 to 0.05. T value is greater than 1.656, so it can be concluded that the H3 is supported, which means there is positive between the training and development of employees' performance.

The results of the t test for job satisfaction obtained t arithmetic amounted to 2.899 with t table value of 1.656 to 0.05. T value is greater than 1.656, so it can be concluded that the H4 supported which means there is positive between job satisfaction and employee performance.

The results of the t test for job satisfaction obtained t calculate equal to 1,999 with t table value of 1.656 to 0.05. T value is greater than 1.656, so it can be concluded that the H9 supported which means there is positive between OCB on employee performance.

Path Analysis

Path analysis was used to test the effect of mediating variables. Path analysis is an extension of multiple regression analysis. Path analysis is used to estimate the causal relationships between variables (causal models).

Table 8 Path Analysis

	Direct Impact	Indirect Impact (via Z)	Total Impact
X1 -> Y	p1 = 0,081	p5p9 = 0,05632	0,13732
X2 -> Y	p2 = 0,056	p6p9 = 0,06336	0,11936
X3 -> Y	p3 = 0,0170	p7p9 = 0,05568	0,07268
X4 -> Y	p4 = 0,139	p8p9 = 0,088	0,277
Z -> Y	p9 = 0,320	-	0,320

Analysis Data

Based on statistical tests that have been conducted on nine hypothesis, it is known that there are nine hypotheses are supported. The discussion of these hypotheses are described as follows.

Based on the results of statistical tests described above, showed that H1 is supported, which means that there is a positive influence between work life policies on employee performance. These results indicate that the performance of employees affected by work-life policies. Based on the results of statistical tests described above, showed that H2 is supported, which means there is positive between empowerment on employee performance. These results indicate that the empowerment received by employees affect its performance. Based on the results of statistical tests described above, indicates that the H3 is supported, which means there is positive between the training and development of employees' performance. These results indicate that the performance of employees affected by the receipt of training and development. Based on the results of statistical tests described above, indicate that the H4 is supported, which means there is positive between job satisfaction on employee performance. These results indicate that job satisfaction is achieved by the employee will have an effect on performance. The higher employee satisfaction in the work, then performance will increase. Vice versa, the lower the satisfaction of

employees in the work, then performance will decrease.

Based on the results of statistical tests described above, shows that H5 is supported which means there is a positive influence between work life policies on employee performance through OCB. OCB may mediate the relationship between work-life policies and employee performance. These results indicate that work-life policies are accepted by employees affected by OCB and will affect the performance generated by the employee. Based on the results of statistical tests described above, indicate that H6 is supported, which means there is positive between empowerment on employee performance through OCB. OCB may mediate the relationship between empowerment and employee performance. Empowerment encourage individuals to seize the initiative in this matter in mediation by the OCB in the completion of their work in a timely manner. These results indicate that the empowerment received by employees affected by OCB and will affect the performance generated by the employee.

Based on the results of statistical tests described above, shows that H7 is supported, which means there is positive between training and development to employee performance through OCB. OCB may mediate the relationship between the training and development of employees' performance. These results suggest that training and development is provided by the university can influence the OCB employee and the resulting performance effect for those employees. Based on the results of statistical tests described above, indicates that the H8 supported, which means there is positive between job satisfaction and employee performance through OCB. OCB may mediate the relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance. These results indicate that job satisfaction can influence OCB employee and the resulting performance effect for those employees. Based on the results of statistical tests described above, indicates that the H9 is supported, which means there is positive between OCB on employee performance. These results indicate that OCB employee can affect its performance.

Conclusion

This study has limitations where this research uses only tenured faculty majoring in business management that is in Batam. For further research may investigate permanent and temporary lecturers. Also advisable in

future studies to examine the performance of employees in all departments. Subsequent research can also add the scope of the study.

References

- Atmojo, M. (2012). The Influence of Transformational Leadership on Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment and Employee Performance. *International Research Journal of Business Studies*, 5(2), 113-128.
- Bernardin, H. John and Russel, E.A., (1993). *Human resource Management, An Experiential Approach*. Mc. Graw Hill International Edition, Singapore: Mac Graw Hill Book Co.
- Cacciope, R. (1998). Structured empowerment: an awardwinning program at The Brunswood Resort. *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 19(5), 264-74.
- Cascio, Wayne. (2003). *Managing Human Resources: Produktivity, Quality of work Life, Profit (6th Ed)*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Cohen, S. (2004). Test anxiety and its effect on the personality of students with learning disabilities. *Journal of Learning Disability Quarterly*, 27(3), 176-184.
- Emerson, R. M. (1976). Social exchange theory. *Annual review of sociology*, 335- 362.
- Elmuti, Dean. Yunus Kathawala. (1997). An Investigation into Effects of ISO 9000 on Participants' Attitudes and Job Performance. *Production and Inventory Management Journal*, Second Quarter.
- Fitrianasari, D., Nimran, U., & Utami, H. N. (2013). Pengaruh Kompensasi dan Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Organizational Citizen Behavior (OCB) dan Kinerja Karyawan. *Jurnal Profit*, 7(1), 12-24.
- Frone, M.R., Russell, M. and Cooper, M.L. (1992). Antecedents and outcomes of work-family conflict: testing a model of the work-family interface. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 77(1), 65-78.
- Gutek, B.A., Searle, S. and Klepa, L. (1991). Rational versus gender role explanations for work-family conflict. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 76, 560.
- Ghozali, I. (2011). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan Program IBM SPSS 19*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Ghozali, I. (2012). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate Dengan Program SPSS*. Semarang: BP Universitas Diponegoro.
- Hariandja, Marihot Tua Efendi. (2002). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia: Pengadaan, Pengembangan, Pengkompensasian, dan Peningkatan Produktivitas Pegawai*. Jakarta: Grasindo.

- Handoko, T. Hani. (2003). *Manajemen*. Cetakan Kedelapanbelas BPFEYogyakarta, Yogyakarta.
- Herrenkohl, R.C., Judson, G.T., dan Heffner, J.A. (1999). Defining and measuring employee empowerment, *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 35(3), 373-389.
- Kazmi, R., Amjad, S., & Khan, D. (2007). Occupational stress and its effects on job performance: A case study of medical house officers of district Abbottabad, *First Proceedings of International Conference on Business and Technology*.
- Kreitner, Robert and Angelo Kinicki. (2001). *Organizational Behavior*. Fifth Edition. Irwin McGraw-Hill.
- Lovell, S. E., Kahn, A. S., Anton, J., Davidson, A., Dowling, E., Post, D., & Mason, C. (1999). Does gender affect the link between organizational citizenship behavior and performance evaluation? *Sex Role*, 41(5/6), 469-478.
- Mahesa, D. (2010). Analisis Pengaruh Motivasi dan Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan dengan Lama Kerja Sebagai Variabel Moderating.
- Mangkunegara, Anwar Prabu. (2004). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan*, Bandung: Remaja Rosda Karya.
- Mangkuprawira, Sjafrri. (2004). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Strategik*. Cetakan ketiga, Penerbit Ghalia Indonesia.
- Noon, M. & Blyton, P. (1997). *The realities of work*. Houndsmills: Macmillan.
- Organ, D. W. & Konovsky, M. (1989). Cognitive versus affective determinants of organizational citizenship behavior. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 74(1), 157.
- Organ, D.W. and Ryan, K. (1995). A meta-analytic review of attitudinal and dispositional predictors of organizational citizenship. *Personnel Psychology*, 48(4), 775-802.
- Organ, D. W. (1988). *Organizational Citizenship Behavior-The Good Soldier Syndrome*. (1st Ed.). Lexington, Massachusetts/Toronto: D.C. Heath and Company.
- Organ, D.W. (1988). *Organizational Citizenship Behavior: The Good Soldier Syndrome*. Lexinton book. Lexington, MA.
- Rogg, K. L., Schmidt, D. B., Shull, C. & Schmitt, N. (2001). Human resources practices, organizational climate and customer satisfaction. *Journal of Management*, 27, 431-449.
- Sadariusman, Eka. 2004. Pemberdayaan: Sebuah Usaha Memotivasi Karyawan, *Fokus Ekonomi*, 3(2).
- Paré, G., Tremblay, M. & Lalonde, P. (2001). The role of organisational commitment and citizenship behaviours in understanding relations between human resources practices and turnover intentions of IT personnel. *Scientific Series #2001s-24*, CIRANO, Montreal, Canada.
- Podsakoff P.M., MacKenzie S.B., Moorman R.H., Fetter R. (1990). Transformational Leader Behaviors and their effects on followers' trust in leader, satisfaction, and Organizational Citizenship Behaviors. *Leadership Quarterly*, 107-142.
- Robbins, Stephen P. (2006). *Perilaku Organisasi*. Edisi kesepuluh. Jakarta: PT Indeks Kelompok Gramedia.
- Tremblay M., Rondeau A., and Lemelin M. (1997). *La mise en oeuvre de pratiques innovatrices de gestion des ressources humaines a-t-elle une influence sur la mobilization*. GRH face h crise: GRH en crise, Presses HEC, 97-109.
- Thamrin, H. M. (2012). The Influence of Transformational Leadership and Organizational Commitment on Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance. *International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology*, 3(5), 566-572.
- Tessema, M. and Soeters, J. (2006). Challenges and prospects of HRM in developing countries: testing the HRM-performance link in Eritrean civil service. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 17(1), 86-105.
- Shahab, M. A., & Nisa, I. (2014). The Influence of Leadership and Work Attitudes toward Job Satisfaction and Performance of Employee. *International Journal of Managerial Studies and Research (IJMSR)*, 2(5), 69-77.
- Sugiyono. (2008). *Metode Penelitian Administrasi*. Bandung: CV. ALFABETA.
- Susanto, L. E. (2008). Analisis Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja, Kepuasan Kerja dan Gaji Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Perusahaan Genteng Press PT. SGN.
- Wulani, F. 2005. Sikap kerja dan implikasi dalam pengelolaan sumber daya manusia: suatu kajian ter hadap organizational citizenship behavior. *Jurnal Studi Bisnis*, 3(1).